

FREE VIBRATION OF DELAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATES WITH CONTACT ANALYSIS

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SUMMARY: The free vibration of composite laminated plates with through-the-width delamination was investigated analytically and experimentally. In analysis, Hamilton's principle and the finite element method were extended to derive the free vibration equation for the delaminated composite plates. The transformation method, which reduced the degrees of freedom of the plate, was applied to deal with the geometric compatibility between the contact surfaces of upper and lower sublaminates in the delaminated region. The free vibration of the delaminated composite plate was treated as a two-dimensional plane-strain eigenvalue problem. In experiment, a shaker system was used to determine the natural frequencies and the corresponding mode shapes for the delaminated plates. The delamination becomes significant to affect the natural frequencies as its size exceeds 50% of the laminate length. The natural frequencies of the delaminated plates decrease with increasing values of fiber orientation and also decrease as the delaminated region located toward the center of the composite plates.

KEYWORDS: free vibration, natural frequency, composite plate, delamination

INTRODUCTION

Owing to high strength/weight ratio, composite materials have been widely used in the aerospace, automobile, defense and civil industries. However, there is occasionally some defects in our daily used materials. Composite materials have defects as well. Delamination is one of the defects encountered in most composite laminated plates. It results from low velocity impact, fatigue loads and manufacturing defects. Therefore, study of influence of delamination on the composite laminates is rather important.

The dynamic characteristics of composite laminates were investigated by Rayleigh-Ritz method [1], Galerkin Method [2, 3], and finite element method [4-10]. Among them, Bhimaraddi [2] studied the effect of initial imperfection on the nonlinear dynamic response of composite laminates; Bicos and Springer [4] derived the free vibration equation of composite laminates with damping by Hamilton's principle; Dhanaraj and Palaninathan [5] and Ju et al. [6] discussed the influence of initial stress on the dynamic characteristics of composite laminates. Shen and Grady [7], Tracy and Pardoan [8] and Ju et al. [9, 10] assessed the dynamic characteristics of composite laminates with delamination. Ju et al. [10] analyzed the contact phenomenon at the delamination; however, they dealt with the case with node pairing only.

Among the methods related to contact mechanics, there are transformation matrix method [11-13], penalty method [14, 15], Lagrangian multiplier [16, 17] and flexibility matrix method [18]. The solution accuracy and stability of penalty method is determined by the magnitude of penalty number and structural stiffness. The Lagrangian multiplier method needs additional parameters. When using the flexibility matrix method, the node pairing on both sides of contacting surfaces is required. The transformation matrix method satisfies the geometric compatibility between the contacting surfaces and reduces the number of degrees of freedom of the problem. It deals with both sticking and sliding conditions on the contacting surfaces, which was not discussed before for the composite laminates; therefore, it was used in this study to obtain the dynamic response of the composite laminates.

In analysis, Hamilton's principle and the finite element method were used to derive the system equation of the composite laminates. The governing equation omitted the damping due to its small effects on the composite laminates [19-21]. For the contact points, the transformation matrix method was used and the contacting conditions were iterated. The free vibration of composite laminates was treated by a two-dimensional plane strain eigenvalue problem to find the natural frequencies and mode shapes. The material properties used in the analysis were obtained from experiment. In experiment, a shaker system was used to obtain the dynamic characteristics of the composite laminates. The size and the position of delamination and the fiber orientation were varied and compared with results obtained from analysis.

HAMILTON'S PRINCIPLE

The contact effects on the free vibration response of composite laminates with through-the-width delamination was investigated in this study. Fig. 1 shows schematic of a cantilever composite laminated plate with through-the-width delamination. Hamilton's principle is expressed as [22]

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \delta(T - U) dt + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \delta W_{nc} dt = 0 \quad (1)$$

where T is the total kinetic energy of the laminate system; U is the potential energy of the system; δW_{nc} is the virtual work done by nonconservative forces; $\delta(\bullet)$ is a variation symbol; t_1, t_2 are the times at which the system configuration is known. Here

$$T = \int_V \frac{1}{2} \rho \dot{\underline{u}}^T \dot{\underline{u}} dv \quad (2)$$

$$U = \int_V \frac{1}{2} \underline{\tau}^T \underline{\epsilon} dv = \int_V \frac{1}{2} \underline{\epsilon}^T [E] \underline{\epsilon} dv \quad (3)$$

$$W_{nc} = W_F + W_C \quad (4)$$

$$W_F = \int_V \underline{u}^T \underline{f} dv + \int_S \underline{u}^T \underline{F} dS \quad (5)$$

$$W_C = \int_{S_c} \underline{u}_A^T \hat{\underline{F}}_{CA} dA + \int_{S_c} \underline{u}_B^T \hat{\underline{F}}_{CB} dA \quad (6)$$

where \underline{u} is the displacement vector; $\dot{\underline{u}}$ is the velocity; ρ is the density; $\underline{\tau}$ is the stress; $\underline{\epsilon}$ is the strain; $[E]$ is the matrix of material constants; W_F is the work done by the nonconservative external force; W_C is the work done by the contact force; \underline{f} is the body force; \underline{F} is the surface tractions; $\underline{F}_{CA}, \underline{F}_{CB}$ and $\underline{u}_A, \underline{u}_B$ are the contact forces and displacements on the surfaces above and below the delamination; $V = V_A + V_B$ and $S = S_A + S_B$ are the volume and surface of the composite laminate; S_c is the contact area.

The contact force $\hat{\mathbf{F}}_C$ must be in equilibrium as $\hat{\mathbf{F}}_C = \hat{\mathbf{F}}_{CA} = -\hat{\mathbf{F}}_{CB}$. Eqn 6 is expressed as

$$W_C = \int_{S_C} (\underline{\mathbf{u}}_A - \underline{\mathbf{u}}_B)^T \hat{\mathbf{F}}_C dA \quad (7)$$

Transformation Matrix

The displacement $\underline{\mathbf{a}}_A$ of an arbitrary contact point p on the surface above delamination is divided into three parts [11, 12] as: (i) gap displacement $\underline{\mathbf{a}}_{p \rightarrow q}$, (ii) sticking displacement $\underline{\mathbf{a}}_{q \rightarrow r}$, (iii) relative sliding displacement $\underline{\mathbf{a}}_{r \rightarrow s}$, as shown in Fig. 2.

$$\underline{\mathbf{a}}_A = \underline{\mathbf{a}}_{p \rightarrow s} = \underline{\mathbf{a}}_{p \rightarrow q} + \underline{\mathbf{a}}_{q \rightarrow r} + \underline{\mathbf{a}}_{r \rightarrow s} = [\mathbf{N}] \underline{\mathbf{a}}_B + \underline{\mathbf{t}} a_s + \underline{\mathbf{h}} = [\mathbf{G}] \underline{\mathbf{a}} + \underline{\mathbf{h}} \quad (8)$$

where $\underline{\mathbf{h}}$ is the gap displacement; $[\mathbf{N}]$ is the matrix of shape function; $\underline{\mathbf{a}}_B$ is the displacement vector of point q below delamination; $\underline{\mathbf{t}}$ is the tangent vector of contact point below delamination; a_s is the magnitude of relative displacement. Eqn 8 is the constraint condition of the contact surface above delamination. $[\mathbf{G}]$ includes $[\mathbf{N}]$ and $\underline{\mathbf{t}}$ and is called the transformation matrix. $\underline{\mathbf{a}}$ is a combination of $\underline{\mathbf{a}}_B$ and a_s . If point p doesn't contact with point on surface below delamination, $[\mathbf{G}]$ is a unity matrix, and $\underline{\mathbf{a}} = \underline{\mathbf{a}}_A$, $\underline{\mathbf{h}} = \underline{\mathbf{0}}$.

Finite Element Method

The two-dimensional isoparametric quadratic element was used in analysis. The laminate is divided into two parts; part A is above the delamination, part B includes regions below the delamination and area without delamination (see Fig. 3). In Eqn 7, $\underline{\mathbf{u}}_A - \underline{\mathbf{u}}_B$ is the relative displacement of points above and below delamination; they can be expressed as $\underline{\mathbf{a}}_{p \rightarrow s} - \underline{\mathbf{a}}_{q \rightarrow r}$, as shown in Fig. 2. After finite element discretization, the work done by the contact force W_C is

$$W_C = \sum_{j=1}^J (\underline{\mathbf{a}}_{p \rightarrow s} - \underline{\mathbf{a}}_{q \rightarrow r})^T (\hat{\mathbf{R}}_C) = \sum_{j=1}^J ((\underline{\mathbf{t}}^T \hat{\mathbf{a}} + \underline{\mathbf{h}})^T (\hat{\mathbf{R}}_C)) \quad (9)$$

where J is the element number above the delamination; $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_C = \int_{S_C} [\mathbf{N}]^T \underline{\mathbf{r}}_C dA$ is the contact nodal force to be determined; $\hat{\mathbf{a}}$ is the nodal displacement produced by contact force $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_C$. Both $\hat{\mathbf{a}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_C$ are to be determined. The total kinetic energy, potential energy and work done by nonconservative external force can be expressed in terms of $[\mathbf{G}]$ and $\underline{\mathbf{a}}$ as

$$T = \sum_{j=1}^{J_A} \frac{1}{2} ([\mathbf{G}] \dot{\underline{\mathbf{a}}} + \dot{\underline{\mathbf{h}}})^T [\mathbf{M}_A] ([\mathbf{G}] \dot{\underline{\mathbf{a}}} + \dot{\underline{\mathbf{h}}}) + \sum_{j=1}^{J_B} \frac{1}{2} (\dot{\underline{\mathbf{a}}})^T [\mathbf{M}_B] (\dot{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}) \quad (10)$$

$$U = \sum_{j=1}^{J_A} \frac{1}{2} ([\mathbf{G}] \underline{\mathbf{a}} + \underline{\mathbf{h}})^T [\mathbf{K}_A] ([\mathbf{G}] \underline{\mathbf{a}} + \underline{\mathbf{h}}) + \sum_{j=1}^{J_B} \frac{1}{2} (\underline{\mathbf{a}})^T [\mathbf{K}_B] (\underline{\mathbf{a}}) \quad (11)$$

$$W_F = \sum_{j=1}^{J_A} ([\mathbf{G}] \underline{\mathbf{a}} + \underline{\mathbf{h}})^T (\underline{\mathbf{Q}}_A) + \sum_{j=1}^{J_B} (\underline{\mathbf{a}})^T (\underline{\mathbf{Q}}_B) \quad (12)$$

where J_A and J_B are the element numbers of part A and part B; $[\mathbf{M}_A]$ and $[\mathbf{M}_B]$ are mass matrices; $[\mathbf{K}_A]$ and $[\mathbf{K}_B]$ are stiffness matrices; $\underline{\mathbf{Q}}_A$ and $\underline{\mathbf{Q}}_B$ are external forces. Since there is only contact force, no external force, on the contact surface, $\underline{\mathbf{Q}}_A = \underline{\mathbf{0}}$, $\underline{\mathbf{Q}}_B = \underline{\mathbf{0}}$, the nodal contact force can be expressed by the nodal force equilibrium above the delamination as $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_C = [\mathbf{K}_A] \hat{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}_A + [\mathbf{M}_A] \hat{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}_A$. The frictional force on the contact surface is expressed according to Coulomb's law as

$$\underline{t}^T \hat{\underline{R}}_C = \text{sign} \cdot \mu_d \cdot \underline{n}^T \hat{\underline{R}}_C \quad (13)$$

where μ_d is the frictional coefficient; \underline{t} and \underline{n} are the tangential and normal vectors on the contact surface. If \underline{a} is replaced by global parameter \underline{a}^* , after substituting Eqns 9 to 13 into Hamilton's principle and rearrangement for zero gap displacement at contact point $\underline{h}^* = 0$ and no external forces $\underline{Q}_A^* = \underline{Q}_B^* = 0$. The system governing equation can be obtained as

$$[[G^*]^T - \mu_d \cdot \text{sign} \cdot [n^*]^T \quad [I]] \left(\begin{bmatrix} [M_A^*] [G^*] \\ [M_B^*] \end{bmatrix} \ddot{\underline{a}}^* + \begin{bmatrix} [K_A^*] [G^*] \\ [K_B^*] \end{bmatrix} \underline{a}^* \right) = 0 \quad (14)$$

Material Properties

The material property of each layer of the composite laminate is assumed as transversely isotropic. There are total of five material constants: Longitudinal modulus E_1 , transverse modulus E_2 , shear modulus G_{12} and Poisson's ratios ν_{12} and ν_{23} , which result in the stress-strain relation of each layer in the fiber principal direction. The material property in the natural coordinate can be obtained by a transformation matrix between the fiber principal direction and the natural coordinate. For simplicity, assume that the composite laminate is under plane strain condition. The stress-strain relation in Cartesian coordinate can be obtained by a transformation matrix between the natural coordinate and Cartesian coordinate.

The Gaussian quadrature was used in numerical integration. For composite laminate, each layer may have different fiber orientation; therefore, the material properties are integrated through layers in the thickness direction. The elemental stiffness matrices $[K_A]$, $[K_B]$ can be obtained through the use of material property matrix in Cartesian coordinate and are assembled to be the global stiffness matrices $[K_A^*]$, $[K_B^*]$ in Eqn 14.

Free Vibration of Laminated Plates

Assuming that \underline{a}^* has the following form.

$$\underline{a}^* = \underline{\Phi} e^{-i\omega t} \quad (15)$$

where $\underline{\Phi}$ is the displacement vector which is not a function of time. After substituting Eqn 15 into Eqn 14, for $\underline{\Phi}$ to have nontrivial solution, let

$$\det([G^*]^T - \mu_d \cdot \text{sign} \cdot [n^*]^T \quad [I]) \left(\begin{bmatrix} [M_A^*] [G^*] \\ [M_B^*] \end{bmatrix} \omega^2 + \begin{bmatrix} [K_A^*] [G^*] \\ [K_B^*] \end{bmatrix} \right) = 0 \quad (16)$$

Eqn 16 is the standard eigenvalue problem, in which the eigenvalue ω is the natural frequency of the system. The composite laminates studied have one end fixed and the other end free. The following boundary conditions were applied to the system.

$$u_i = 0, \quad v_i = 0, \quad dv_i / dx = 0 \quad (17)$$

where u_i , v_i are the displacements in the x- and y-direction at the fixed end, respectively. From the solution obtained from Eqn 16, the eigenvector $\underline{\Phi}$ can be found to represent the natural mode shapes of laminated plate.

EXPERIMENT

In addition to the finite element analysis, the shaker vibration experiments were performed to verify the analytical results. The size and location of delamination and the fiber orientation were varied to assess their effects on the dynamic response of the laminated plate. The composite specimens were made from graphite/epoxy prepregs (0.12mm thick per ply) with required size and stacking sequence. They were put in an aluminum mold on a temperature-controlled hot press. In the upper region of the aluminum mold air pressure was applied on top of the specimen; while a vacuum pump was used to empty the gas produced during the curing process. For the delaminated specimens, a Teflon piece (0.1 mm thick) was imbedded to form an artificial delamination.

The material property of a single composite layer is assumed as transversely isotropic. Five material constants E_{11} , E_{22} , G_{12} , ν_{12} , ν_{23} are needed, in which $\nu_{23} = \nu_{12}$ is assumed as conventional [23, 24]. The rest four material constants were measured on a tensile testing frame according to ASTM D3039 [25]. Each constant was obtained by the average of three experiments as $E_{11} = 147.27 \pm 6.09$ Gpa, $E_{22} = 13.89 \pm 1.04$ Gpa, $G_{12} = 4.87 \pm 0.15$ Gpa, $\nu_{12} = 0.320 \pm 0.032$.

Shaker Vibration Experiment

The specimens used in shaker vibration experiment had length 200 mm, width 40 mm and 8 layers. One end of specimen was fixed for 50 mm, the test section had 150 mm long. Before the experiment, proper position for force sensor and sampling points for output signal were layout on surface of the laminate specimen. The specimens were then fixed on the test fixture and shaker, amplifier, signal analyzer, force sensor, accelerometer connected as arranged in Fig. 4. The force sensor was glued on the specimen. The accelerometer was used to measure the dynamic response at each sampling point. During the experiment, an excitation was generated by the signal analyzer, amplified and connected to the shaker. The shaker forced the specimen to vibrate. The signals from force sensor and the accelerometer on the laminate specimen were amplified and fed into the signal analyzer to obtain the frequency response function by fast Fourier transform (FFT). The response function was directed into a personal computer in which the STAR Modal System was used to calculate the natural frequencies and mode shapes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, the free vibration of composite laminates with through-the-width delamination was analyzed by the finite element method and was verified by shaker vibration experiment. The position and size of delamination and the fiber orientation were varied to evaluate their influence on the dynamic response of the laminated plates. Fig. 5 shows three-dimensional mode shapes obtained from shaker vibration experiment for specimen ($w=40$ mm, $L=150$ mm, $D=1.1$ mm, $a/L=2/3$, $d/D=1/8$, $[0^\circ]_8$). The first and third mode shapes are bending types. The second mode shape is a torsional one which can't be obtained from plane strain analysis. Fig. 6 shows the corresponding two-dimensional bending mode shapes from the middle section. Fig. 7 shows the corresponding natural modes obtained from the finite element analysis. The analytical first mode shows a bulge-up separation in the middle delaminated region, while it is not shown in the experimental results due to counter effect of

the weight of accelerometer on the weaker upper delaminated region. The second bending modes agree well in both analytical and experimental results. Because of high noise and poor signal acquisition at higher frequency, the third bending mode was unable to found in experiment; however, the analytical third bending mode showed a contact point in the middle of delamination.

Variation of Delamination Size

The size of delamination was varied for laminated specimens to find its influence on the dynamic response of composite laminates. The sizes of delamination were $a/L=1/4$, $1/2$, $2/3$ and $5/6$. The separate movement of the delaminated region occurs for delamination size larger than 50% of laminate length. Figs. 8 and 9 show the relation between the bending natural frequencies and delamination size for laminated specimens ($w=40$ mm, $L=150$ mm, $D=1.1$ mm, $d/D=1/8$, $[0^\circ]_8$). In Fig. 8, the natural frequencies of the first bending mode decrease with the delamination size. Larger reduction can be seen for delamination size larger than $2/3$. The trend of analytical results was consistent with the experimental ones. In Fig. 9, the natural frequency of the second bending mode for $a/L=1/2$ and $2/3$ were larger than those of laminates without delamination, since separating movement occurred for the delaminated region. The bulge-up of delaminated region increases the bending rigidity of laminate which results in higher natural frequency for $a/L=1/2$ and $2/3$. As the length of delamination increases, the upper delaminated region becomes weaker; therefore, the additional rigidity obtained from the bulge-up movement was smaller and natural frequencies decrease as also observed in experiment.

Variation of Delamination Position

The position of the delamination in the thickness direction of specimens was varied to evaluate its effect on the dynamic response of the laminate plates. The positions of delamination are $d/D=1/8$, $2/8$ and $4/8$. Figs. 10 and 11 show the relation between the natural frequencies and delamination position for laminated specimens ($w=40$ mm, $L=150$ mm, $D=1.1$ mm, $a/L=2/3$, $[0^\circ]_8$). The natural frequencies of the first bending modes decrease as the delamination position toward the center of specimen. The experimental natural frequencies for specimens with $d/D=1/8$ is lower than those of the specimens with $d/D=2/8$ due to the difficulty in manufacturing the former specimens. The specimens with $d/D=1/8$ probably changed their local thickness at the delaminated region. For the second bending modes, the natural frequencies for specimens with $d/D=1/8$ and $d/D=2/8$ are higher than those of specimens without delamination. This can be explained from separating movement for mode shapes of specimens at the delaminated region. The bulge-up delamination gave extra bending rigidity for the composite laminates. For the case with delamination position at the mid-thickness $d/D=4/8$, no separating movement found in the bending mode; thus, the bending rigidity decrease and natural frequencies decrease as well.

Variation of Fiber Orientation

The delaminated plate specimens ($w=40$ mm, $L=150$ mm, $D=1.1$ mm, $a/L=2/3$, $d/D=1/8$) were used with variation of fiber orientation θ to evaluate its effect for laminates with $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$ stacking sequence. The stacking sequences were $[0^\circ]_8$, $[\pm 30^\circ]_{2S}$, $[\pm 45^\circ]_{2S}$, $[\pm 60^\circ]_{2S}$ and

$[\pm 90^\circ]_{2S}$. Figs. 12 and 13 show bending natural frequencies for specimens with different fiber orientation. The bending natural frequencies decrease with fiber orientation for both first and second bending modes. The natural frequencies decrease more quickly for θ between 0° and 45° . The plane strain finite element method can only predict reasonable results for cross-ply laminated plates which is symmetric about the middle section in the longitudinal direction.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the free vibration of composite laminates with through-the-width delamination was investigated analytically and experimentally. The two-dimensional finite element analysis was used to calculate the natural frequencies and mode shapes for the delaminated composite plates. The shaker vibration experiment was carried out to verify the analytical results. The following conclusions can be made:

- (1) The natural frequencies of the delaminated plates decrease as delamination size increases. This effect is more significant for cases with delamination near upper surface of specimen and size larger than $a/L=2/3$.
- (2) For laminated plates with small delamination, no local separating movement at delaminated region occurs and their natural frequencies are close to composite plates without delamination.
- (3) The natural frequencies of the delaminated plates usually are smaller than those of laminated plates without delamination; however, for some cases e.g., $a/L=2/3$, $d/D=1/8$, the local separating movement adds bending rigidity which increases the natural frequencies to a higher value than those of laminates plates without delamination.
- (4) When the delamination position is at mid-thickness of the laminated plate, no local separating movement occurs and the natural frequencies are much lower than those laminated plates without delamination.
- (5) The natural frequencies of the delaminated plates decrease as the fiber orientation increases for laminates with stacking sequence $[\pm\theta]_{2S}$.

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Fig. 1: Schematic of a cantilever composite plate with through-the-width delamination.

Fig. 2: Schematic of contact nodal displacement.

Fig. 3: Schematic of finite element mesh for delaminated plate.

Fig. 4 Arrangement of shaker vibration experiment.

Fig. 5 Experimental three-dimensional mode shapes for specimen with $w=40$ mm, $L=150$ mm, $D=1.1$ mm, $a/L=2/3$, $d/D=1/8$ and $[0^\circ]_8$.

Fig. 6 Experimental two-dimensional mode shapes for specimen with $w=40$ mm, $L=150$ mm, $D=1.1$ mm, $a/L=2/3$, $d/D=1/8$ and $[0^\circ]_8$.

Fig. 7 Analytical mode shapes for specimen with $w=40$ mm, $L=150$ mm, $D=1.1$ mm, $a/L=2/3$, $d/D=1/8$ and $[0^\circ]_8$.

Fig. 8 First bending natural frequencies for laminated specimens ($w=40$ mm, $L=150$ mm, $D=1.1$ mm, $a/L=2/3$, $d/D=1/8$, $[0^\circ]_8$) with different delamination size.

Fig. 9 Second bending natural frequencies for laminated specimens ($w=40$ mm, $L=150$ mm, $D=1.1$ mm, $a/L=2/3$, $d/D=1/8$, $[0^\circ]_8$) with different delamination size.

Fig. 12 First bending natural frequencies for laminated specimens ($w=40$ mm, $L=150$ mm, $D=1.1$ mm, $a/L=2/3$, $d/D=1/8$) with different fiber orientation.

Fig. 10 First bending natural frequencies for laminated specimens ($w=40$ mm, $L=150$ mm, $D=1.1$ mm, $a/L=2/3$, $[0^\circ]_8$) with different delamination position.

Fig. 13 Second bending natural frequencies for laminated specimens ($w=40$ mm, $L=150$ mm, $D=1.1$ mm, $a/L=2/3$, $d/D=1/8$) with different fiber orientation.

Fig. 11 Second bending natural frequencies for laminated specimens ($w=40$ mm, $L=150$ mm, $D=1.1$ mm, $a/L=2/3$, $[0^\circ]_8$) with different delamination position.